

Articles

Anshuman Behera*

Emerging Trends of Terrorism: A Critical Analysis

Abstract

Study of terrorism, a much-debated topic, has so far been understood and engaged with, mostly from a security perspective. Accordingly, in its various forms and shades, terrorism is perceived to be a serious security threat to both, the states and all the individuals, individually residing in them. Despite the difficulties in terms of coming to a consensual position of defining the term, terrorism continues to pose serious security threats to many states. A majority of the countries, in their efforts to curb terrorism, have adopted multiple methods.

However, the dominant commonality in terms of their responses to curb terrorism is limited to addressing the issue from a territorial point of view. Most countries see their success against their responses against terrorism in terms of the terrorist activities in and around the respective territorial boundaries. Engaging with terrorism to the extent of its operational framework within a particular territorial framework offers very limited understanding of the issue, both at the policy and academic levels. It has been observed that states, in their effort to curbing terrorism in their respective territorial boundaries, have only witnessed a limited success for a very short span of time. Terrorism, as it is evolving in its very nature and scope, keeps throwing surprises in multiple ways in terms of spectacular attacks, mode of operation and time and space of its strikes. With an objective to engage with the changing scenarios of terrorism, this article intends to highlight major trends of terrorism. In the process of identifying the emerging trends of terrorism, the article also critically engages with the conceptual aspects of the issue and to a certain extent, the remedial measures worth considering.

Introduction

The understanding of terrorism, especially in terms policy responses to curb it, has been mostly seen from the perspectives of how much of a security threat

* **The author** is Assistant Professor, Conflict Resolution Program, National Institute of Advanced Studies (NIAS), Bengaluru, India.

it poses to a state. The aspect of security threat, in this context, is seen through the extent of fatalities it causes and its presence within the territorial framework of a state. Such an understanding is a shared commonality among the majority of the states directly or indirectly affected by the acts of terrorism, today.

The United States' (US) report on 'Country Reports on Terrorism 2016' (CRT) reflects on this aspect of the current understanding of terrorism. In the CRT report it is mentioned that: "although terrorist attacks and fatalities resulting from such terrorism declined globally for the second year in a row in 2016, terrorist groups continued to exploit ungoverned territory and on-going conflict to expand their reach, and to direct and inspire attacks around the world".¹ Further, it also mentioned that "regional and international military coalitions supported to varying degrees by the United States and its allies continued to make progress against terrorist groups in fragile states, particularly in Africa."² Notwithstanding the widely believed notions on terrorism, the acts of terrorism defy national boundaries to make it trans-national in character. The spatial and rapid growth of terror networks globally has prompted responses from various agencies, both state and non-state. The immediacy of the issue has also prompted diverse opinions about terrorism. Narratives such as 'your terrorist is my freedom fighter' are making the issue more complex as there are more disagreements than consensus over the issue. Considering the changing nature of terrorism, this article makes an attempt to critically engage with the emerging trends of terrorism. The first part of article engages with the conceptual aspects of terrorism and drawing on the conceptual framework, the second part of the article deals with the emerging trends.

Understanding Terrorism: Towards a Conceptual Framework

Understanding terrorism has never been an easy task considering the lack of consensus among the nation states and various international agencies on the issue. 'Terrorism', a serious challenge to mankind, as a whole entity, has been viewed differently in the various states, depending on the stand point they believe in. A lack of a definition, or a widely accepted one, (both extremes of the same spectrum) is what the human right organisations call the risk of abuse and an invitation to abuse. The human rights organisations are of the opinion that in countries with no legal definition or rather vague ones, it might be very tempting for governments, especially for governments of a more authoritarian nature.³ The lack of a clear and agreed upon definitional framework, in many cases, is seen to be used by the many such states against its citizens, labelling them as terrorists, who otherwise, in most cases, have no intention of using any violent means against fellow individuals or against the state they live in, for that matter.

When it comes to the definitional framework of terrorism, there exists more than one definition on the issue. Most of these definitions have been offered by the regional organisations or international bodies.

The 1999 United Nations (UN) Convention for Suppression of the Financing Terrorism as per Article 2(1)(b) defines terrorism as ‘Any act intended to cause death or serious bodily injury to a civilian, or to any other person not taking an active part in the hostilities in a situation of armed conflict, when the purpose of such act, by its nature or context, is to intimidate population or to compel a government or an international organization to do or to abstain from doing an act.’⁷⁴

The Security Council of the United Nations in its resolution 1566 (2004) referred to terrorism as “criminal acts, including any act against civilians, which is committed with the intent to cause death or serious bodily injury, or taking of hostages, with the purpose to provoke a state of terror in the general public or in a group of persons or particular persons, intimidate a population or compel a Government or an international organization to do or to abstain from doing any act.”⁷⁵

Similarly, the Article 1(2) of the Arab Convention for the Suppression of Terrorism, signed at Cairo on April 22, 1998, defines terrorism as “any act or threat of violence, whatever its motives or purposes, that occurs in the advancement of an individual or collective criminal agenda and seeking to sow panic among people, causing fear by harming them or placing their lives, liberty, or security in danger, or seeking to cause damage to the environment of public or private installations or property, or to occupying to seizing them, or seeking to jeopardize a natural resource.”⁷⁶

The Convention of the Organization of the Islamic Conference on Combating International Terrorism states in the Article 1(2) that “Terrorism means any act of violence or threat, thereof, notwithstanding its motives or intentions, perpetrated to carry out an individual or collective criminal plan with the aim of terrorising people or threatening to harm them or ‘imperilling’ their lives, honour, freedom, security or rights or exposing the environment or any facility or public or private property to hazards or occupying or seizing them, or endangering a national resource, or international facilities, or threatening the stability, territorial integrity, political unity or sovereignty of independent states.”⁷⁷

From the many definitions cited above, there emerge a number of common points on defining terrorism. Uncertainty of violent action is an important common point that emerges from the above mentioned definitions on terrorism.

The terror attacks are usually carried out rather randomly. This randomness, possibly, could be with intent to instil a sense of paranoia among the public regarding ‘safe behaviour’, creating a psychosis that anyone could be the next victim.⁸ The terror attacks do not always target directly. It is not only the people who die, but even the ones who live, who are indirect targets of terror. A second important common point here is the aspect of vulnerability. The uncertainty of the terror attacks that they can take place anywhere, anytime or against anybody makes almost everyone vulnerable. The third aspect of terrorism that creates incredible fear is the ‘helplessness’. This helplessness rules the mind of the general public, the state apparatus and the society as a whole. The inability of the state apparatus to secure its citizens enhances the sense of helplessness. The fourth aspect is ‘personalisation’. The individual who has never experienced any terror attack is a target, and is as vulnerable, or perhaps more vulnerable than someone who has already been a victim.

Despite the above-mentioned definitions and common aspects of terrorism, there are also areas of disagreement. One of the major issues leading to such disagreements is the widespread assumption that ‘one man’s terrorist is other’s freedom fighter’. On this confusion Richard Chasdi, is of the opinion that

Terrorism is a ‘means’ to an end and hence, to compare ‘terrorism’ as a means, to ‘freedom’, which is a goal or ‘end’, is thereby in effect logically flawed. When ‘freedom’ is the goal pursued over the political landscape, what that essentially means...is freedom to pursue ‘self-determination’ as mentioned in the Charter of the United Nations in Chapter I article 2.⁹

Similarly, Ajai Sahni, a leading scholar on terrorism opines that,

The justifications of terrorism in terms of liberation struggle, freedom fighting, etc. are derived from questionable or fallacious reasoning. Take, for instance, the ‘one man’s terrorist’ argument. This is clearly based on contra-factual demand for the uniqueness of identity. The fact is a man has multiple identities....He may...be a freedom fighter and a terrorist; the first identity defines what he fights for, the second, the method he employs.... ‘Freedom fighters’...cannot reconcile an act of random and wanton violence that terminates the very possibility of freedom for innocent others within any consistent ethical paradigm. The murder of innocents would be unacceptable within virtually any concept of ‘just war’. Even as there can be no ‘just genocide’, ‘just terrorism’ can or should not make any real sense in legitimate political discourse. It is only because these arguments have not been widely articulated or debated that the confusion, and hence the ambivalence, over terrorism has persisted in both public and policy circles.¹⁰

Based on the above discussions, this article seeks to clarify the understanding on terrorism. In this article, by terrorism it is meant: an act of violence, which aims to instil fear among the innocent people, who are not necessarily the primary target of the terrorists. While the means of carrying out terror activities remains to be violent, the goals and the targets of the terrorists remain unclear. Beyond instilling fear among the people, the objective of the terrorists can be understood through two different schools of thoughts.

Terrorism with its multiple interpretations and objectives has evolved through the passing years. Engagement of multiple actors (both state and non-state), advancements in technology and the changing world order have brought about many changes in the style and functioning of terror groups in the recent years and thus, their reach and effect has expanded substantially in the recent years. Though elements such as fear, violence, and destruction of property remain constant in all terror activities, there have also emerged new trends in the recent years. The next section of the article highlights some of the major trends of terrorism.

Emerging Trends of Terrorism

State vs. Non-state: Blurred Distinctions

Terrorists and the terror groups as non-state actors has been a dominant and widely accepted narrative in the strategic and security studies. Terror organisations have been seen as non-state actors as they are perceived to be functioning independent of individual state support and are beyond the control of the state. There exists a body of literature dealing with the threat emanating from the non-state actors. Such an understanding on terrorists as non-state actors helps strengthen our belief that the modern state systems do not involve in terror related activities. Hence, the state's right to use coercion against its citizens is both legitimate and legal. The terror groups functioning within the territory of different states are necessarily illegal and illegitimate actors.

Against such a narrative, the terror activities in the recent years have blurred the distinction between state and non-state actors. The rapidly changing world order is witnessing increasing involvement of states in promoting, funding and sustaining terror groups. The state actors or agencies are seen to be initiating, pursuing and determining the outcomes of terror related activities. The role of Inter Service Intelligence (ISI) in funding and sustaining many terror groups in South Asia can be cited as an example. Studies conducted on the role of ISI and its links with many terror groups in Pakistan, India, and Bangladesh corroborate such claims.¹¹ India's allegation against Pakistan for providing a safe haven to

the terrorist groups can be seen as the involvement of the Pakistani state with terror groups. The assumption that has been discussed above in this article on ‘one’s terrorist is another’s freedom fighter’ helps states like Pakistan, legitimising its support to many terror groups present in its territory. The Prime Minister of Pakistan, Nawaz Sharif’s, address to Burhan Wani, the former commander of Hizbul Mujahideen who was killed by the Indian Security forces, as a dynamic leader and a freedom fighter¹² is a testimony to the assumption.

Apart from Pakistan, the world has also seen other major powers involved in supporting one terrorist groups or the other. The United States of America’s support in the rise of Al Qaeda against the Soviet Union during the Cold War is an open secret. The major powers are seen to be using terror groups for maximising their national interests. These days China has been seen opposing India’s move in the UN to declare Masood Azhar, Chief of Jaish-e-Mohammad (JeM) as a global terrorist. China claims his opposition against India’s move as professional and objective.¹³ Masood Azhar led JeM has carried out many terrorist attacks in India killing and injuring a number of people. However, China’s support to Masood Azhar further blurs the distinction between state and non-state actors. The increasing involvement of state powers in supporting one terrorist group or the other is a major worrisome feature of many terrorism studies.

America-Centric Approach of Understanding Terrorism

Arguably, the terror attacks on 11 September 2001 (popularly known as 9/11) in the USA is considered as the ‘watershed moment’, that changed the dynamics of reacting to terrorism. The 9/11 was not the first terror attack, but it was certainly a major attack and that too against the most powerful state in the world. The Al Qaeda led, 9/11 attack on the American soil prompted the *US-led war* against ‘Global Terrorism’. While many terror attacks, prior to the 9/11 attack were seen as incidents against a particular country, the 9/11 attacks were given a global colour. Ever since the ‘America led NATO’ forces invaded the Taliban government in Afghanistan to crack down on the Al Qaeda and its associate organisations, many countries apart from the NATO members have changed their perspectives in dealing with the terrorism. The entire dynamics of understanding terrorism and dealing with the same have under gone drastic changes post the 9/11 terror attacks. The presence of American and the NATO forces in South Asia, especially in India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan, in the name of fighting against global terrorism has also affected the security dynamics in this region. The Indian state’s policies in dealing with the terror groups were also influenced by the post 9/11 narratives. The decision to ban the

Students' Islamist Movement in India (SIMI)¹⁴ immediately after the 9/11 attacks were a case in point.

The terrorism scenario post 9/11 has also witnessed increasing involvement of US in many terror related theatres. Starting from Afghanistan to Iraq and Syria, the active involvement of the US and supporting nation states make the issue more serious. A US centric understanding and dealing with terrorism has led to two prominent scenarios. First, there has been selective coverage of terror actors and terror theatres. The involvement of US forces in 'combating terrorism' determines the coverage and highlighting of the various terror groups and theatres. This also validates the US's presence and involvement in almost all major places affected by terrorism. The US forces have been seen actively involved in Afghanistan, Iraq, Syria, Yemen, Libya and Somalia. These places feature more in the headlines, in comparison to other places as well as incidents affected by terrorism.

Secondly, the frequent involvement of the US and other supporting states has created a counter narrative, declaring the US as a terrorist state. The 'violence, fear and destruction of property' due to the attacks by the US forces are seen by many states, intellectuals, and the terror groups as heinous acts of terror. Noam Chomsky, a leading scholar, called the US as the 'world's leading terrorist state' due its frequent interventions in the domestic politics of other states in the pretext of countering terror.¹⁵ Moreover, many terrorist groups, mostly the Islamic Ones, have an anti-America narrative to justify their fight. In one of his speeches against the US, Hafiz Saeed, the head of the Pakistan based terrorist group, Lashkar-e Taiba (LeT), said that, "America has been fighting against the entire Islamic world under the garb of 9/11 attacks...."¹⁶ Similarly, the literature of Islamic State in Iraq and Syria (ISIS) has anti-American narratives.¹⁷ The Islamic terror groups have 'successfully' manufactured a narrative that the American action in the name of fighting against global terrorism is against Islam as a whole. Such anti-American feeling has been a major instrument, used by most of the terror groups for recruitment activities. In a way, the increased involvement of the US has sustained many of the terror groups.

Growing Radicalisation and the Youth

Radicalisation as a term connotes many meanings. For the purpose of this paper, I use the definition given by Charles E Allen that says that "radicalization is a process of adopting an extremist belief system, including the willingness to use, support, or facilitate violence, as a method to effect societal change".¹⁸ This definition mostly covers the many aspects used by other scholars in understanding radicalisation in relation with terrorism studies. The growing

radicalisation, especially among the youth across the globe is one of the major trends of terrorism. The radicalisation among the youth is mostly intertwined with certain political agenda and not just terrorism. A number of studies have already been conducted, especially in the European countries, to understand the root causes of youth radicalisation and several counter-radicalisation measures have been taken to deal with the issue. Most of these studies focusing on the aspect of fathoming the root cause, deal with burning issues such as poverty, psychology of the youth, unemployment, ideological indoctrination, etc.¹⁹

In most of the European countries, the factors that have led to radicalisation among the youth, especially the Muslim youth, are a demand for an equal status, contested identity among the second generation Muslim youths, and the effects of Iraq and Syria,²⁰ and thus, basic Islamic fundamentalism. Similarly, the Asian and African states are also experiencing growing religious radicalisation among the Muslim youth. The major commonalities found experienced through the process of radicalisation across the globe are discussed below.

In most of the cases, the radicalised youth are seen to be fighting for a 'larger cause'. The concept of a larger cause, in the case of terrorism, among the Muslim youth, is mostly based on the narratives to protect Islam from the atrocities of the non-believers, supremacy of Islam over all other beliefs and against the perceived attacks on Islam. These narratives highlighting the larger cause of Islam dilute individual identity and goals. Death in this regard is glorified and portrayed as achieving martyrdom. The methods used in radicalising the youth have developed drastically in the last few years. The availability and easy accessibility of literature on Islamic fundamentalism in social media, internet, etc. have been major sources of radicalisation. Radical organisations such as Hizb-ut-Tahrir (HuT)²¹ have been important actors in radicalising Muslim youth in many countries. Thus there has been an increasing number of self-radicalised youth in the recent times. The instances of 'Lone wolf' attacks by self-radicalised youths have gone up.

The radicalised youth have also been a major source of recruitment for many terrorist groups. While the major terror groups play vital roles in radicalising the youth, the self-radicalised youth volunteer as recruits for the former. Groups such as ISIS attracts many like minded youth from many other countries to fight along with its regular recruits in Syria. As many as 22 radicalised youth from the state of Kerala have been reported to have joined the Islamic state in 2016.²² At the same time, we have instances where self-radicalised youths carry out terror activities in many countries, and ISIS claims the responsibility

of such activities. The terror attacks in Bangladesh, France and Germany are the instances in this regard. Arguably, such are the new trends in terrorism.

Though the radicalised youth play an important role in the sustenance of a terror group, they are mostly confined to the ‘fighters’ level i.e. they are generally the followers. Very few young recruits are actually at the leadership or decision-making positions. The leadership continues to be with the old guards like Hafiz Saeed, Ayman al-Zawahiri, Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi, etc. The youth are merely used as cannon fodder.

Incidents with High Casualties

Terror activities including the 9/11 attack and other subsequent ones are carried out, intending to cause massive casualties. While the number of terror attacks, post 9/11 has gone up, the number of lives lost is also substantially high. The 9/11 attack alone had killed around 3000 people including the terrorists. The Mumbai 2008 terror attacks, admittedly carried out by LeT claimed as many as 166 lives. The use of high-end communication technology by the terrorists and the availability of explosives, guns and other weapons of destructions provide an advantage to the terror groups. Better coordination among the terrorists, thanks to developed communication technologies, has also been instrumental for the wider networks of the terror groups.

At the same time, the terrorists have also discovered alternative, newer targets and more devious ways of carrying out terror attacks. For last few years, it has been observed that the terrorists are targeting large human gatherings. The methods and weapons used in the terror attack on Charlie Hebdo in France in January 2015 and the Berlin attack in December 2016 are quite different. In case of the Charlie Hebdo attack, the terrorists used sophisticated guns to kill the people, whereas in Berlin, the terrorist drove a truck through a gathering killing many people. While the ideological motives behind the Charlie Hebdo attack appeared to be clear, it was difficult to attribute a reason for the Berlin terror attack. Similarly, the self-radicalised terrorists’ attack in a restaurant in Dhaka, Bangladesh was targeted against the ‘western culture’. Though the Bangladesh security forces recovered a huge cache of explosives and guns from the deceased terrorists, it was reported that most of the 28 people who were killed were brutally murdered using sharp weapons.²³ The high number of casualties caused by the terror attacks instils even more fear and anxiety among the public.

Religious vs. Ideological Terrorism

Religious terrorism, mostly Islamic, has played a major role in replacing

extremism based on Leftist ideology. Militant groups guided by religious fanaticism have replaced the withering militant, communist movements in South and South East Asian countries. Bangladesh can be cited as an example in this regard. The extremist groups based on militant communist ideology such as Purba Banglar Communist Party (PBCP) and its various factions, Communist Party of Bangladesh (CPB), and Gana Fauz, etc. have been completely eliminated by the Islamist terrorist groups such as Jamaat-ul-Mujahideen-Bangladesh (JMB)²⁴ and Jagrata Muslim Janata Bangladesh (JMJB).²⁵

Where India is concerned, there exist multiple types of militant groups, which use terror methods to further their own interests. In India, there are prominent Islamist groups such as Indian Mujahideen (IM),²⁶ Hizbul Mujahideen,²⁷ and Students' Islamist Movement in India, (SIMI)²⁸ which are guided by the extremist version of Islam. They are believed to be operating in association with terrorist groups outside the Indian Territory. The objectives of these groups are both local as well as international. They seem to organise and strengthen their organisations through the local narratives and at the same time they contribute to the much larger 'Islamist Cause'. Apart from these above mentioned groups, the Communist Party of India-Maoist, (CPI-Maoist).²⁹ Maoists in short, is another armed group, which has been termed as a single largest internal security threat to India. With an active presence in over 80 districts in Central and Eastern parts of India, the Maoists also resort to terror methods to achieve their state objectives. Similarly, India has been fighting a number of militant groups in its North Eastern parts that are constituted on ethnic lines.

While there exist multiple armed groups, that use terrorism as a method of furthering their own personal interests, even the groups with a religious identity, are often termed as terrorists. This seems to be becoming a dominant pattern in many countries. Religious armed groups, especially the ones that are Islamists, are perceived as a threat to 'mankind' and they are then treated as common enemies. Groups such as ISIS, Al Qaeda, LeT, Boko Haram, Al Shabab and many others have been termed as global terrorist groups. While many of these groups operate within a specific territorial boundary, it is sheer perception that puts them in the 'global terrorist' bracket. Groups such as Maoists in India are often not seen as terrorist groups as they are perceived to be fighting for a 'genuine cause'. The 'revolutionary violent'³⁰ paths that the Maoists follow for achieving their objectives are often legitimised by a set of intellectuals. Hence, the whole issue of the security perspective of understanding terrorism is limited to rather a few groups.

Terrorism an Instrument to Acquire Lootable Resources

While factors such as poverty and economic discrimination can no longer be the only proximate causes leading to terrorism, it can be argued that the latter is being used as an instrument to acquire loutable resources. This aspect of terrorism highlights high economic stakes involved in the entire process. Literature in this respect suggests involvement of ISIS in illicit business of petroleum and other products.³¹ Similarly, terror groups like the Haqqani Network is allegedly involved in a nefarious money making business.³² While funds and finances definitely play a very important role for sustaining terror groups, many terror groups make a lot more money, much more beyond their need. Involvement of large amounts of money distances the terror groups from their ideology and goals that they claim to be fighting for. In such scenarios, sustaining terror activities appears profitable for the groups rather than ideological as they proclaim. The diversion from the original goal and ideology by the terror groups blurs the distinction between organised criminal groups and a terror group.

Spaces of Terrorism

Terrorism, in recent times, operates in multiple spaces such as territorial space, informal space and imagination space. The target objectives of terrorism at these various spaces are appreciably different in nature. If one considers it from the point of the national territory space, it (terrorism) targets high attention areas, i.e. critical infrastructures, where there can be a higher casualty rate and much loss of infrastructure. From the imaginary space point of view, it creates fear to accentuate the extent of threat, and at the same time it attempts to create a world view to legitimise its actions. And from the viewpoint of an informal space, it plans its activities with the help of other agencies; (not necessarily the terrorists) here, terrorism prefers absence of violence and underplays the threats so that informal networks are not disrupted. In this space, the terror networks use social media as a platform for propaganda purposes. At the national stage, the terrorists also provoke the state for retaliation with the prime motive to further alienate the vulnerable minds that can be tapped for future terrorist activities. In this process, the terrorists attempt to make divisions in the society and tap the like-minded groups.

Conclusion

The strategies to deal with terrorism, across many countries, have tended to be confined to the territorial dimensions. Individual countries formulate policies targeting specific acts of terror and most of the times, these policies are designed to combat the terrorists with the final aim of eliminating them. While it cannot be denied that the territorial dimensions remain critical in order to deal with

acts of terror, the other important dimensions and aspects of the situation also need to be taken seriously.

For example, the functioning of radical groups, such as Hizb-ut-Tahrir does not necessarily come under the territorial dimensions. Understanding the very ideology and doctrines that radicalise the youth, will help us understand the terror movements that they lead to, better. The coordination among the countries and states need not be confined to the tactical and strategic levels only. They need to see the entire process of terrorism and the factors leading to the acts of terrorism, rather than just dealing with the incidents which arise thereof. The terror groups, in the recent years, have been substantially targeted by the security agencies in different countries. Such actions have further led to the development of smaller and diffused groups, rather than diffusing the terrorist activities and a potentially violent atmosphere. The terror attacks carried out by the smaller and diffused groups pose newer challenges, as the difficulty levels in identifying these groups is growing much higher. The ‘lone Wolf’ attacks carried out by the self- radicalised youth is a new emerging trend, and it needs to be addressed; nipped in the bud, to say precisely. Strategies dealing with the territorial dimension of terrorism are not proving to be the end-game answer to these trends.

The rise in the acts of terrorism across many countries has also prompted many of them to respond militarily, paradoxically contributing to more violence in the process of combating the terrorists. The violence and the counter violence by the terror groups and by the states, respectively, appear to be a never-ending process, forming a vicious circle leading to more violence at this point of time. The states, as responsible actors should be duty bound to reduce the violence level. Alternative measures in terms of negotiation, de-radicalisation of youth, the social security of the deprived communities, etc needs to be implemented with a greater spirit towards reducing and minimising the violence levels.

Notes

1. “Country Reports on Terrorism 2016”, <https://www.state.gov/documents/organization/272488.pdf>, accessed on 20 July 2017.
2. *Ibid.*
3. “Lecture 6 - 1.5 Need For a Definition: Some Attempts”, <https://www.coursera.org/learn/terrorism/lecture/QOvXP/1-5-need-for-a-definition-some-attempts>, accessed on 10 October 2016.
4. “A more secure world: Our shared responsibility”, Report of the High-level Panel on Threats, Challenges and Change, United Nations, 2004, http://www.un.org/en/peacebuilding/pdf/historical/hlp_more_secure_world.pdf, accessed on 10 October 2016.
5. “Security Council Acts Unanimously to adopt Resolution strongly condemning Terrorism as one of the most serious threats to Peace”, United Nations Meeting Coverage and Press

- Release, 08 October 2004, <http://www.un.org/press/en/2004/sc8214.doc.htm>, accessed on 10 October 2016.
6. "The Arab Convention on the Suppression of Terrorism", 22 April 1998, https://www.unodc.org/tldb/pdf/conv_arab_terrorism.en.pdf, accessed on 10 October 2016.
 7. "Convention of the Organization of the Islamic Conference (OIC) on Combating International Terrorism", July 1999, <http://www.cfr.org/terrorism-and-the-law/convention-organization-islamic-conference-oic-combating-international-terrorism/p24781>, accessed on 10 October 2016.
 8. J. Horgan, *The Psychology of Terrorism*, London: Routledge, 2005, p. 3.
 9. Alex P. Schmid, *The Routledge Handbook of Terrorism Research*, London: Routledge, 2011, p. 21.
 10. Ibid. pp. 21-22.
 11. SK Sharma, and Anshuman Behera, *Militant Groups in South Asia*, IDSA, New Delhi: Pentagon Press, 2014.
 12. "Nawaz Sharif ticks off India again on Burhan Wani, Kashmir", *The Times of India*, 05 January 2017, http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/world/pakistan/nawaz-sharif-ticks-off-india-again-on-burhan-wani-kashmir/article-show/56357237.cms?TOI_browser_notification=true
 13. "China responds to India on Masood Azhar, says its stand is 'professional and objective'", *Times of India*, 05 January 2017, <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/world/china/china-responds-to-india-on-masood-azhar-says-its-stand-professional-and-objective/articleshow/56359637.cms>.
 14. Anshuman Behera, "The Students Islamic Movement of India: The Story So Far.", *Journal of Defence Studies*, Vol-7, Issue-1, January-March 2013, pp- 213-228.
 15. "Noam Chomsky calls US 'world's leading terrorist state'", 04 November 2014, <https://www.rt.com/usa/202223-noam-chomsky-global-terror/>.
 16. "Hafiz Saeed Speech Against India and America at Pakistan", <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MsmNHvJO2FE>
 17. Graeme Wood, "What ISIS Really Wants", *The Atlantic*, March 2015, <http://www.theatlantic.com/magazine/archive/2015/03/what-isis-really-wants/384980/>, accessed on 16 October 2016.
 18. Charles E. Allen, "Threat of Islamic Radicalization to the Homeland", Testimony before the U.S. Senate Committee on Homeland Security and Government Affairs, 14 March 2007, p. 4.
 19. Lorenzo Vidino and James Brandon, "Countering Radicalization in Europe", A policy report published by the International Centre for the Study of Radicalisation and Political Violence (ICSR), 2012, pp. 7-69.
 20. Robert S. Leiken, "Europe's Angry Muslims", Council of Foreign Relations, July/August 2005, <http://www.cfr.org/religion/europes-angry-muslims/p8218>, accessed on 16 October 2016.
 21. n. 11, pp. 279-286.
 22. "22 missing Kerala youth traced to ISIS training camp in Afghanistan", <http://www.abplive.in/india-news/22-missing-kerala-youth-traced-to-isis-training-camp-in-afghanistan-sources-475750>.
 23. "Dhaka cafe attack ends with 20 hostages among dead", *The Guardian*, 03 July 2016, https://www.google.co.in/webhp?hl=en&ictx=2&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwiy_Muf26_RAhXLLY8KHQ39CkIQPQgD#hl=en&q=Restaurant+attack+in+Dhaka.

24. N. 11, pp. 13-24.
25. South Asia Terrorism Portal, <http://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/bangladesh/terroristoutfits/JMJB.htm>.
26. Shishir Gupta, 'Indian Mujahideen', *Hachette India*, Gurgaon, 2011.
27. n. 11, pp. 39-45.
28. Behera, n. 14, pp. 213-228.
29. n. 11, pp. 115-123.
30. Manoranjan Mohanty, *Revolutionary Violence: A Study of Maoist Movement in India*, New Delhi: Sterling Publishers, 1977.
31. Ashley Fantz, 'How ISIS makes (and takes) money', *The CNN*, 20 February 2015, <http://edition.cnn.com/2015/02/19/world/how-isis-makes-money/index.html>, accessed on 20 July 2017.
32. 'Haqqani network is 'addicted to war profits'', *The National*, 03 August 2012, <https://www.thenational.ae/uae/haqqani-network-is-addicted-to-war-profits-1.444315>, accessed on 20 July 2017.